

IMPACT RESPONSE OF PARTICLE-REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

An experimental and analytical study of the impact behaviour of ceramic particle-reinforced metal matrix composites is presented. The impact behaviour is characterized using Taylor cylinder impact tests and deep penetration tests. The penetration test results show an increasing resistance to penetration with increasing volume fraction of reinforcement. The cylinder impact tests indicate an increasing yield strength with increasing reinforcement volume fraction as well as with higher rates of loading. The dynamic yield strengths are used in an analytical cavity expansion model to predict penetration depths.

KEYWORDS: Metal Matrix Composites; Taylor Test; Dynamic Strength; Impact Response

INTRODUCTION

Particulate reinforced metal matrix composites (MMC) have the known advantage of higher modulus, strength, hardness, and wear resistance and the disadvantage of lower strain to failure, higher cost and difficulty of processing compared to their monolithic matrix materials [1]. However, there is little or no information on their behaviour under high velocity impact loading. This paper presents experimental results on ceramic particulate reinforced aluminum matrix composites and analyzes them using simple closed form solutions developed for monolithic metals.

MATERIALS

Two MMC systems, both based on the 6061 aluminum matrix, were selected. One, available from Duralcan, is an alumina particle reinforced system made by a liquid metallurgy (LM) route (rheocasting) with nominal reinforcement volume fractions of 10, 15, and 20%. The other, available from DWA Composites, is a silicon carbide particle reinforced system made by a powder

metallurgy (PM) route, with 0, 15, and 30% reinforcement volume fractions. Both systems were extruded and subjected to a standard T6 ageing treatment. A high strength LM7075-T6 aluminum alloy was also included in the test program to compare with the MMC materials.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Tension Tests

Tension tests were performed at room temperature in a screw-driven Instron machine at a constant displacement rate of 0.005 cm/min, corresponding to an initial strain rate of $0.66 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Small button-end specimens (ASTM B557-81) were cored and machined from the extruded bars. Strains were measured using a strain gauge extensometer.

Taylor Cylinder Impact Tests

To measure the high strain-rate material properties, the Taylor impact test technique was used [2]. This test consists of impacting a short flat-ended cylinder of the material of interest on a flat rigid anvil at normal incidence. Within a certain range of impact velocities, the cylinder deforms plastically in a mushroom-like shape. If the velocity is too low, there are no measurable plastic deformations, whereas if the velocity is too high, cracking and fracture can occur. Therefore, the less ductile the material, the narrower the range of velocities where useful results can be gathered. From measurements of the deformed shape and knowledge of the original kinetic energy, the average dynamic strength can be calculated.

Details of the testing apparatus are provided in [3]. Of interest here are that the rigid anvil was a hardened steel cylinder, with its impact face lubricated to minimize any frictional effects at the specimen/anvil interface. The cylindrical test pieces were 11.56 mm in diameter and 23.18 mm in length. Depending on the ductility of the materials involved, the specimens were launched at velocities ranging from 150 to 300 m/s.

Dynamic Penetration Tests

The dynamic penetration tests were conducted using the same system mentioned above. The tests consisted of firing a small rigid tungsten rod with a hemispherical nose shape into a cylinder of the material of interest. The projectiles were 4.48 mm in diameter and 27 mm in length and had a nominal mass of 7.1 grams. They were inserted in polycarbonate sabots that fitted the diameter of the launch barrel. The targets were cylindrical specimens with a nominal diameter of 50 mm and a length of 150 mm. This was considered to be sufficiently long that the effects of boundary conditions on the penetration response could be neglected. Tests were performed at three average impact velocities of 475, 750 and 920 m/s. The specimens were then X-rayed to determine the cavity profiles. Some specimens were also sectioned and subjected to metallographic examination.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Tension Test Results

Table 1 provides a summary of these results as well as other relevant material properties. The tensile stress-strain curves for the LM 6061-T6 Al and DWA-30 MMC are shown in Figure 1. The stress-strain curve for the MMC specimen exhibits nonlinearity starting at low strains. The addition of 30% SiC reinforcement leads to increases of 50% in modulus and 20% in strength, at the expense of a reduction in ductility from 17% to 1.5%. The DWA-30 material fails in a brittle fashion with no necking.

Taylor Impact Test Results

Taylor tests were performed on LM 6061, DURAL-15, DWA-30 and LM 7075 specimens. Both axial and radial specimens of the DWA-30 were tested. Measurements of the tested specimen profiles revealed that the radial deformations were not axisymmetric. This asymmetry of plastic deformation can be attributed to an anisotropy in yield strength. Figure 2 shows the percentage of asymmetry (A) versus distance from the impact face for both axial and radial specimens. The radial specimen exhibits a higher degree of asymmetry than the axial specimen. Figure 3 shows a comparison between the deformed profiles of the two specimens, calculated by taking an average value of the major and minor radii (i.e. R and r in Figure 2). The radial specimen is slightly softer than the axial one, thus indicating that the dynamic strength properties of DWA-30 are somewhat anisotropic. This material also appeared to be susceptible to radial cracking at the impact face. These cracks, caused by large radial expansions, are not unexpected given the low ductility of the material.

Dynamic Penetration Test Results

The penetration depths at various impact velocities are shown in Figure 4. In Figure 5 the penetration depths at 750 m/s for all the MMCs are plotted as a function of the reinforcement volume fraction. The PM-processed materials are more resistant to penetration than the LM-processed materials, with the difference being more significant at higher volume fractions. For the MMC specimens, depth measurements were complicated by the fact that in some cases the penetrator and the cavity were bent. This may have been caused by areas of higher strength or hardness due to higher local volume fractions of particles. At low velocities (475 m/s), the DWA-30 material always exhibited three large radial cracks on its impact face. Examination of the sectioned specimen showed that the crack patterns were similar to the Hertzian-type cracks observed in static indentation of brittle materials such as ceramics. At higher velocities, where both confining pressures and strain-rates are high, the DWA-30 specimen looks similar to a typical ductile metal specimen. It is also interesting to note from Figure 4 that the unreinforced LM 7075 material exhibits a slightly deeper penetration than the DWA-30 MMC, despite its slightly superior static strength properties. The above results suggest that factors such as high pressures and strain-rates play important roles in the local strengthening of MMCs and hence their penetration resistance.

DYNAMIC STRENGTH PREDICTIONS

The dynamic strength can be inferred using a number of one dimensional wave propagation analyses applied to the results of a Taylor cylinder impact test. We use two representative methods here [4,5], although all give similar results and trends [3].

Model of Hawkyard

Hawkyard [4] assumed a rigid-plastic material model and invoked an energy balance across the plastic wave front to arrive at the following equation for an estimate of the mean dynamic yield strength (Y_D)

$$Y_D = \frac{1}{2} \rho V^2 / \left\{ \ln \left(\frac{1}{1-e} \right) - e \right\} \quad (1)$$

where ρ and V are the density of specimen and initial impact velocity, respectively, and e is a plastic strain measure defined as

$$e = 1 - X/L_0 \quad (2)$$

L_0 and L_f are the initial and final total lengths, and X is the final undeformed section length as shown in Figure 3. If measurements of X are not available, the quantity e can be determined implicitly in terms of the geometry of the test-piece by the following expression

$$L_f = L_0 (1 - e) [1 - \ln(1 - e)] \quad (3)$$

The mean dynamic yield strength Y_D can be estimated by solving Eq. (3) iteratively for e and substituting the result in Eq. (1). Also, an estimate of the mean strain-rate is given by $V/(2L_0e)$.

The calculated values of the mean dynamic yield strength and strain-rate are shown in Figure 6. Also shown are the dynamic strength data obtained by Ross *et al.* [6] and Nicholas [7] using Hopkinson bar test arrangements. From these limited data it appears that the yield strength of DWA-30 is more strain-rate sensitive than that of the unreinforced aluminum. This may partially explain the slightly better penetration performance of the DWA-30 compared with the LM 7075 unreinforced aluminum.

Model of Jones et al.

Jones *et al.* [5] used a similar analysis to Hawkyard but modified it to account for the mass transfer from the rigid to the plastic segment. Thus

$$Y_D = \rho V^2 \beta / e \quad (4)$$

where β is given by the following transcendental equation:

$$L_f/L_0 = \beta e^2 / (1 + \beta e) - \{ \beta e (1 - e) / (1 + \beta e)^2 \} \ln [\beta (1 - e) / (1 + \beta)] + (1 - e) \quad (5)$$

Sensitivity studies [3] indicate that the dynamic yield strength values are more sensitive to errors in measurements of L_f than to errors in X . Furthermore, both models appear to be sensitive to errors in impact velocity measurements. The mean dynamic strength values calculated using both methods are listed in Table 1.

PENETRATION DEPTH PREDICTIONS

The penetration depths were predicted using the cylindrical cavity expansion model developed by Forrestal *et al.* [8]. This model is attractive since it is a closed form solution involving only a few measurable parameters. The final penetration depth (P) for a spherical tipped rod penetrating a semi-infinite, elastic-perfectly plastic target is given by

$$P = \frac{m}{2\beta_s} \ln[1 + \beta_s V^2/\alpha_s] \quad (6)$$

where

$$\alpha_s = \frac{2}{3} \pi a^2 Y_D \left\{ 1 + \ln \left[\frac{E}{3(1-\nu)Y_D} \right] \right\} (1 + \mu\pi/2) \quad (7)$$

$$\beta_s = 1.041(\pi a^2 \rho/2)(1 + \mu\pi/4) \quad (8)$$

In Eqs (6) to (8), E , ν , Y_D , and ρ are the elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio, dynamic yield strength, and density of the target respectively, m and a are the projectile mass and radius, and μ is the coefficient of friction at the projectile/target interface. Substituting values of Y_D obtained from the Hawkyard analysis (see Table 1) and setting $\mu = 0.08$, a reasonable fit to most of the experimental penetration data can be achieved, as shown in Figure 2. However, the model by Hawkyard overpredicts the penetration depth of the DWA-30 material. Therefore, for this material the predicted line is based on the model by Jones *et al.* In general, analytical models are useful for determining trends, but more sophisticated numerical hydrodynamic codes are necessary for detailed modelling. As higher reinforcement volume fractions and higher impact velocities are considered, a numerical approach becomes more necessary.

CONCLUSIONS

The yield strength of the MMCs increases more rapidly with strain rate than the unreinforced aluminum. The penetration performance of the MMC is better than the unreinforced matrix, and the relative improvement increases with both increasing reinforcement volume fraction and increasing impact velocity. Simple one dimensional analyses predict the overall trends reasonably well, even though they cannot provide a detailed description of the response.

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Table I - Material Properties

Material	ρ (kg/m ³)	E (GPa)	ν	Y_s (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	ϵ_f (%)	$Y_D^{(H)}$ (MPa)	$Y_D^{(J)}$ (MPa)
LM 6061	2.70	69	0.33	276	310	17	403	471
DURAL-15	2.86	88	0.32	317	359	5.4	524	620
DWA-30	2.85	117	0.27	411	456	1.5	678	807
LM 7075	2.80	71	0.33	503	572	11.3	766	849

Y_s = static tensile yield strength at 0.2% strain offset; $Y_D^{(H)}$ and $Y_D^{(J)}$ = dynamic yield strength calculated using the Hawkyard and Jones analyses respectively; ϵ_f = true failure strain calculated assuming incompressible plastic flow.

Figure 1 - Comparison of the tensile behaviour of DWA-30 MMC (30% SiC in 6061-T6 Al) and unreinforced 6061-T6 Al.

Figure 2 - Comparison of the asymmetry of the plastic deformation profiles for axial and radial DWA-30 Taylor impact specimens. Asymmetry is defined as $A = (R - r)/\sqrt{Rr}$

Figure 3 - Average deformation profiles for axial and radial DWA-30 Taylor impact specimens. Note that the figure is not to scale.

Figure 4 - Measured and predicted penetration depths as a function of impact velocity.

Figure 5 - Decrease in penetration depth as a function of reinforcement volume fraction for both MMC systems.

Figure 6 - Increase in dynamic yield strength as a function of strain rate for both reinforced and unreinforced aluminum.

